

THE UNIVERSITY OF
SYDNEY

seqeralabs

Unlocking nf-core - customising workflows for your research

18 & 19 May 2023

Archive of questions from the workshop Slack Channel

(In the order they were asked during the workshop)

Question/comment	Answer
I'm having some problems logging in. It keeps timing out.	This is usually caused by an institutional firewall blocking connection with Nimbus. Try connecting using a different internet connection.
Can you please remind me how to open the workshop website on VScode?	Copy url of materials website, ctrl shift p to open command palette, then search for simple browser: show, select it, paste url in, hit enter!
Can NF use Mamba instead of Conda?	https://www.nextflow.io/docs/edge/conda.html#use-mamba-to-resolve-packages nf-core default 'nextflow.config' file defines a number of profiles that can be applied to access tools. to use mamba, supply '-profile mamba' in your run command Can also use -useMamba or -useMicromamba in the Conda scope/profile setting.
Would you recommend mamba over singularity/docker?	If you've never used Mamba, I really recommend giving it a go because it's much faster than Conda. Singularity/Docker would be the top preference, but if you are going to use Conda, then probably try Mamba. There is a lot of training available to use containers,

	and it's a lot easier than one might think!
Does the pipeline have to be built with the nf-core template in order to download with the pull command?	No, it doesn't.
Does the nextflow executable contain all previous versions, or does the version variable cause it to download an older version?	It will download the older version.
<p>I have an error when running</p> <pre>nextflow run nextflow-io/hello.</pre> <pre>N E X T F L O W ~ version 23.04.1 Project `nextflow-io/hello` is currently stickied on revision: v1.1 -- you need to explicitly specify a revision with the option `-r` in order to use it</pre> <p>and when I run</p> <pre>nextflow run nextflow-io/hello -r v1.1</pre> <pre>N E X T F L O W ~ version 23.04.1 NOTE: Your local project version looks outdated - a different revision is available in the remote repository [3b355db864] Nextflow DSL1 is no longer supported - Update your script to DSL2, or use Nextflow 22.10.x or earlier</pre>	<p>The versions v1.1 and v1.2 are in DSL1, which is not compatible with the latest version of Nextflow.</p> <p>Run `nextflow run nextflow-io/hello -r master`</p> <p>This will run the latest version, that is in DSL2</p> <p>You can see the versions of the workflow available by using the <code>info</code> option, ie</p> <pre>nextflow info nextflow-io/hello</pre>
<p>“Project `nextflow-io/hello` is currently stickied on revision: v1.1” wasn't something I got - how do things get stickied?</p>	<p>It means you have multiple versions of the pipeline, so you need to specify which to use.</p> <p>When you are running a remote project, nextflow will cache the workflow. If you have multiple, you do need to specify. Which is why you did not need to do it for the very first run, where you had no cached workflow versions, and the default (master) was used.</p> <p>This is explained here: https://nf-co.re/usage/troubleshooting#warning-about-sticked-on-revision</p>

<p>Does the caching mechanism work in a similar way if the storage isn't a traditional filesystem (s3 etc)?</p>	<p>Yes, but the config difficulty and cost is higher (assuming using AWS style commercial provider).</p> <p>AWS configuration documentation is here https://www.nextflow.io/docs/latest/config.html#scope-aws</p>
<p>Where in a nf pipeline should test datasets and e.g. references be located? In assets?</p>	<p>You can set the location of the test dataset in the text.config profile, for example for the rnaseq workflow, check out https://github.com/nf-core/rnaseq/blob/master/conf/test.config</p> <p>As an nf-core parameter, test_data_base param can be changed on the command line or via a parameters file (covered in Lessons 2.1/.2.2). We won't cover the test data param, but as a parameter, you can change it using these methods.</p> <p>Regarding best practice of where to host the test data:</p> <p>Test data is not included in a pipeline's repository, it is pulled from an external source when you run the test profile See: https://nf-co.re/docs/usage/tutorials/nf_core_usage_tutorial#running-pipelines-with-test-data</p>
<p>I saw other pipelines specifying github links for test datasets in the test config. However, I couldn't get that to work for my pipeline because I use a glob pattern to find fastq files in the specified input directory. This does not work when specifying the github parent directory as input directory. Do you have a recommendation for that? Or is it bad practice by now to use a regex to look for fastq files in the input directory?</p> <p>It is about a NF pipeline I am working on, not built with the template.</p>	<p>It's not bad practice to specify inputs as all files in a directory, its just not nf-core current best practices.</p> <p>I'm not sure on the rules/permissions re: using nf-core test data when you are running a non-nf-core pipeline.</p> <p>You could always make your own tiny test dataset and include it in your github repository to be downloaded with your pipeline codebase.</p> <p>In terms of using a samplesheet type input instead of everything in a directory, you</p>

	<p>could follow something like this to use some nextflow operators to map fields in a file as separate inputs https://github.com/Sydney-Informatics-Hub/Nextflow_DSL2_template/blob/main/guides/process_inputcsv.md</p> <p>This is a great resource for writing nextflow patterns https://nextflow-io.github.io/patterns/index.html</p> <p>Answer part 2:</p> <p>Generally, at least with nf-core, you would have a samplesheet with sample names and file paths. If you check out the samplesheet input for any pipeline you can see examples of this. I see you're using wildcards already which is great. I've never tried this straight from github but I'm assuming it won't work very well. This is a module to download recursively from github. You can see how it's used here. I would recommend moving to a samplesheet input if you can.</p>
<p>If a config file cannot overwrite parameters, why does this test.config use the params scope? https://github.com/nf-core/maseq/blob/master/conf/test.config</p>	<p>the sneaky workaround here is the use of the <code>profile{}</code> scope...BUT only some parameters can be used this way</p> <p>This is a tricky point. You have the <code>Nextflow.config</code> file in the main repo and inside this you have <code>includeConfig</code> statements (e.g., line 208). This is most of the way down the hierarchy and you would expect anything configured here should be overwritten using <code>-c</code>. However, this isn't always the case. The way nf-core workflows are structured there is a kink that allows nextflow to interpret the parameters for modules/processes (anything with the <code>params</code> scope) earlier</p>

	<p>and changes you make using parameters in a custom config the <code>-c</code> can be interpreted and applied. This is an unexpected behaviour. The parameters included using <code>includeConfig</code> in the <code>nextflow.config</code> are fine and will behave as you would expect. The same applied to institutional configs. There are exceptions - any parameter that isn't used by a module but is used by the workflow (e.g., <code>params.max_cpus</code>) can be included in a config file. As a rule - put parameters in parameters files and save yourself a headache when some parameters don't work as you expect. If you are trying to apply a parameter in a config file with <code>-c</code> - test and check. You can't trust the stout you see in the command line because it is interpreted at a different time and may be different to what is actually happening.</p>
<p>I get an error if I name the config file as <code>custom.config</code></p> <pre>N E X T F L O W ~ version 23.04.1 Not a valid params file extension: custom.config -- It must be one of the following: json,yml,yaml</pre> <p>runs fine if it is renamed <code>customconfig.json</code></p> <p>Is it just fussy about suffixes? Seemed to work on Chris' terminal. (running fine so not an issue, just curious)</p>	<p>I did some weird stuff right at the end there so sorry for the confusion. <code>.config</code> for <code>-c</code> and <code>.json</code>, <code>.yaml</code>, or <code>.yml</code> for <code>-param-file</code>. Be careful with how the files are written or they won't be interpreted properly.</p>
<p>I'm confused by the different treatment of params and config files. Why is it not possible to provide a customised config file, yet there is a <code>-c</code> option? In other words,</p>	<p>here are lots of different 'scopes' for configuring a workflow. Any 'scope' can go into the a config file that you include with <code>-c</code> except for the params scope. You could still put the parameters scope in the config file but it won't be applied reliable. This is because of <code>'includeconfig'</code> in the <code>nextflow.config</code> file (in the main repo) is</p>

what the purpose of the `-c` option if not to provide a config file?

including the `modules.config`, and this is interpreted and applied by nextflow before the `-c` config is interpreted. In other words, it breaks the normal hierarchy. As a general rule, anything that is utilized by a module won't be applied from a config file you include using `-c`.

You will see in Session 2 that some parameters can be applied with the `params` scope in a config file and the `-c` option. This is generally because they are applied to the workflow and not a module. If you can, apply parameters with `-params-file` and the command line rather than `-c`.

Some extra info - sorry some of this is duplicated 😓

You have the `nextflow.config` file in the main repo and inside this you have `includeConfig` statements (e.g., line 208).

This is most of the way down the hierarchy and you would expect anything configured here should be overwritten using `-c`.

However, this isn't always the case. The way `nf-core` workflows are structured there is a kink that allows nextflow to interpret the parameters for modules/processes (anything with the `params` scope) earlier and changes you make using parameters in a custom config the `-c` can be interpreted and applied.

This is an unexpected behaviour.

The parameters included using `includeConfig` in the `nextflow.config` are fine and will behave as you would expect. The same applied to institutional configs.

There are exceptions - any parameter that isn't used by a module but is used by the workflow (e.g., `params.max_cpus`) can be included in a config file.

As a rule - put parameters in parameters files and save yourself a headache when some parameters don't work as you expect. If you are trying to apply a parameter in a

	<p>config file with <code>-c - test</code> and check. You can't trust the stout you see in the command line because it is interpreted at a different time and may be different to what is actually happening.</p>
<p>If I am running through an institution HPC, what should I put for <code>? Define \$NXF_SINGULARITY_CACHEDIR for a shared Singularity image download folder? [y/n]:</code></p>	<p>Yes.</p> <p>It sounds like you're cache wasn't set to the same folder so when Nextflow went looking for the images they weren't there and started downloading again.</p> <p>It will take about 15-20 mins to run.</p>
<p>My rnaseq pipeline / module is redownloading everything. Doesn't seem to have remembered anything from yesterday. I think my singularity_cache cleared itself somehow?</p> <p>I had to re-export my cache path too this morning. I probably did something weird</p>	<p>No, that's normal because we didn't put that in the <code>~/bashrc</code> file. Just doing <code>export</code> on the command line only lasts until you close your terminal. You didn't do something weird.</p>
<pre>nextflow run nf-core-rnaseq-3.11.1/workflow/main.nf --help NEXTFLOW ~ version 23.04.1 Pulling nf-core-rnaseq-3.11.1/workflow ... Remote resource not found: https://api.github.com/repos/nf-core-rnaseq-3.11.1/workflow/contents/main.nf</pre>	<p>Check that the repo has downloaded into your session 2 dir</p> <p>copy the command from earlier in the content...</p> <pre>training@nf-core-workshop-5-43:~/session2\$ pwd /home/training/session2 training@nf-core-workshop-5-43:~/session2\$ ls -lt total 4 drwxrwxr-x 4 training training 4096 May 19 03:11 nf-core-rnaseq-3.11.1</pre> <p>Background: Nextflow will look for a workflow locally before it looks remotely. Your command will be <code>nextflow run nf-core-rnaseq-3.11.1 --help</code></p> <p>Assuming you're in the same working directory as the folder</p>

<pre>ERROR ~ Unable to read script: '/home/training/session2/nf-core-rnaseq -3.11.1/workflow/./workflows/rnaseq.nf' -- cause: /home/training/session2/samplesheet.csv -- Check script 'nf-core-rnaseq-3.11.1/workflow/main.nf ' at line: 46 or see '.nextflow.log' file for more details</pre>	<p>Do you have the samplesheet.csv file within your session2 dir?</p> <p>You may have missed the command to take the first 3 lines of the remote samplesheet to a local copy</p>
<p>Out of curiosity, why is the <code>--max_memory '6.GB'</code> defined like <code>6.GB</code> with the dot? Is that a nextflow convention?</p> <p>Noticed the same for the <code>--max-time</code> setting too in the help text.</p> <pre>--max_time [string] Maximum amount of time that can be requested for any single job. [default: 240.h]</pre>	<p>You can use both. You could use quotes with a space or without quotes using a dot: <code>"10 GB"</code> or <code>10.GB</code></p>
<p>I used to modify the strandedness in the samplesheet.csv file - is that ok too?</p>	<p>Yes definitely. we just used this as an exercise that could demonstrate you can override that on the CLI or params file.</p>
<p>Why is the label "process_high" for STAR_ALIGN not defined in modules.config?</p>	<p>It's defined as a directive in the module itself: https://github.com/nf-core/modules/blob/master/modules/nf-core/star/align/main.nf</p> <p>You could have the resource labels defined/configured in one big config file with all the modules but it would be harder to read and update. Having them separate makes it easier for developers.</p>
<p>Is there a method to specify multiple process in withLabel in case you have loads? eg. withLabel process_[low/medium/high] to set it for all?</p>	<p>You can specify all using some kind of selector expressions. See here: https://www.nextflow.io/docs/latest/config.html#selector-expressions</p> <p>This will be applied to every process/module that has that label.</p>

	<p>My last comment was about this Nextflow Tower feature. You can access this as a free user and will look at the resources used in a previous run and come up with a custom config that used <code>withName</code> for every process and allocate cpus and memory.</p> <p>https://seqera.io/blog/optimizing-resource-usage-with-nextflow-tower/</p> <p>It won't predict your requirements but will give you optimised resources based on your previous run(s)</p>
<p>I just thought I'd check, if you specify a workflow version with <code>-r</code> can I safely assume that all tool versions are consistent regardless of whether you use singularity, docker, conda (?)</p>	<p>Yes - every version has containers/images/tools that are version controlled. It's a requirement of nf-core workflows that all tools should have a specific version.</p> <p>They should all match between the software managers and you can see changes between versions of a pipeline using the changelog</p>
<p>Would it be a good practice to have both args and version in one trimgalore config file?</p>	<p>It would depend on what you were trying to do and how regularly you were doing it.</p>